

ON THE SPACE-TIME SPECTRUM FOR COMMUNICATION & RADAR SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a method to allocate space-time spectrum to a set of non-uniformly distributed transmitter/receiver pairs is described. Based on the proposed method, efficient transmission of the information is assured. Specifications on the co-channel, the off-channel and the inter-modulation interference will also be met. The presented results are directly applicable to the spectrum management of communications among space-based and land-based stations.

I. Introduction

The spectral interference on a communication system has been evaluated by the *National Telecommunications and Information Administration* (NTIA) through mapping the locations of the transmitter and the receiver [1]. Recently, the distribution of the spectral resources to geographically separated users has been analysed using the *Spectrum Use Factor* (SUF) [2]. The SUF can be considered as the probability that a randomly chosen frequency band will be available for a set of users that are uniformly distributed in space. The assumption of a *uniform user distribution* poses difficulty in most practical applications.

In this paper, no restriction is imposed on the relative geometry of the spatial distribution of the transmitters and receivers. The usage of the space-time spectrum can be optimized by applying the *Space-Time Statistical Modulation Theory* [3]. The maximum transfer of information can be accomplished by matching the rate and the volume of the *quaninfs* with the rate and the available volume of the channel. The general classification of the space-time spectrum is summarized in Table 1. It is clear that the characterization of the space-time spectrum is an important step in the design and the management of a global distributed satellite communication network, see Figure 1.

The ionospheric effects (spatial and temporal signal spread) on the satellite channel had been studied [4]. With a priori knowledge of the space-time channel bandwidth, one can proceed with the allocation of the spectral resources to the users. After the frequency bands are assigned, the interference due to co-channel, adjacent-channel and intermodulation distortion can be evaluated. The results are shown in Section II. In practice, the successful operation of a satellite link requires the interference power to be kept below a maximum level determined from the link budget. A spatial grid for the frequency

assignment scheme is needed. This grid for the base-stations constitutes the inverse problem, which is solved in Section III. Finally, a conclusion of the analyses is shown in Section IV.

II. Allocation of Spectral Resources

Satellite communications through an ionospheric channel can be characterized in terms of the *System Field Tensor* (SFT) $\mathcal{M}(\vec{r}; t)$. When the specification on the space/time and the space/time frequency spread of the satellite network is known, optimal allocation of the network resources is possible. From the gain pattern of the transmitting antenna, interference to the adjacent receivers can be evaluated. Narrow beam width implies high resolution and large spatial frequency. Similarly, short pulse requires large temporal bandwidth.

The spectrum assignment is constrained upon the minimization of the co-channel-rejection, the off-channel-rejection and the inter-modulation products. The observed electric field at the i th band and at the j th frequency re-use on the surface $a_{i,j}$ can be expressed in terms of the noise, $\vec{N}(\cdot)$ and the interference, $\vec{J}(\cdot)$:

$$\vec{E}_o^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t) = \mathcal{M}^*(\vec{r}; t)\vec{E}^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t) + \vec{N}^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t) + \vec{J}^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t), \quad (1)$$

By applying the Wiener-Khinchin Theorem to the space-time correlation function of the observed field, the *power spectral density* (p.s.d.) is obtained. The interference to the i th band at other location $a_{i,l}$ can be expressed in terms of the p.s.d. of the observed field;

$$P_o = \max_{a_{i,l} \in \mathcal{A}'} \left\| \int_{\Omega_i} \int_{B_{a_{i,l}}} \vec{S}_o^{i,j}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\|, \quad (2)$$

where

$B_{a_{i,l}}, \Omega_i$ are the spatial and temporal bandwidth for the i th band at $a_{i,l}$,

$\mathcal{A} \triangleq \{a_{i,j} : \text{The surface area covered by the } i\text{th frequency and the } j\text{th frequency re-use.}\}$ and

$\mathcal{A}' \triangleq \{a_{i,l} : \forall a_{i,l} \in \mathcal{A}, \text{ but } a_{i,l} \neq a_{i,j}\}$.

Therefore, the gain margin for the co-channel-rejection (CCR) with compensation for path loss through the medium must be greater than P_c . To evaluate the off-channel-interference, an assumption on the receiver bandwidth has to be made. When a band pass filter (BPF) with an equivalent receiver bandwidth is used, the observed field becomes

$$\vec{E}_f^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t) = F^*(\vec{r}; t) \vec{E}_o^{i,j}(\vec{r}; t) \quad (3)$$

The maximum power of the off-channel-interference is

$$P_o = \max_{a_{m,n} \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}} \left\| \int_{\Omega_m} \int_{B_{a_{m,n}}} \vec{S}_f^{i,j}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\|, \quad (4)$$

where $\vec{E}_o(\vec{r}; t)$ has been previously defined and the set $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is

$$\tilde{\mathcal{A}} \triangleq \{a_{m,n} : \forall a_{m,n} \in \mathcal{A}_T, \text{ and } a_{m,n} \notin \mathcal{A}\}.$$

From equation (4), the off-channel-rejection (OCR) must be greater than P_o . The third source of interference is the inter-modulation products. This is commonly generated by the square-law-device. The electric field generated by the cross product of the k th and u th bands is

$$\vec{E}_m^{k,l;u,v}(\vec{r}; t) = \sum_{\alpha \in x,y,z} E_{o\alpha}^{k,l}(\vec{r}; t) E_{o\alpha}^{u,v}(\vec{r}; t) \hat{u}_\alpha \quad (5)$$

where \hat{u}_α denotes the unit vector. The corresponding power of the inter-modulation interference is

$$P_i = \max_{a_{k,l}, a_{u,v} \in \mathcal{A}_T} \left\| \int_{\Omega_i} \int_{B_{a_{k,l}}} \vec{S}_m^{k,l;u,v}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\| \quad (6)$$

where $a_{k,l}, a_{u,v}$ are elements in \mathcal{A}_T , the set of surface area with inter-modulation products.

III. The Inverse Problem

For all digital/analog communication links, the *bit error probability* (BER) is a function of the *signal to interference ratio* (SIR). Thus, the system performance is dependent on the co-channel, the off-channel and the inter-modulation interference. A solution of the inverse problem is needed for spectrum management. The problem can be stated as choosing a set of surface areas $\{a_{i,l}, a_{m,n}, a_{k,l}$ and $a_{u,v}\}$ s.t.,

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{a_{i,l} \in \mathcal{A}'} \left\| \int_{\Omega_i} \int_{B_{a_{i,l}}} \vec{S}_o^{i,j}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\| &\leq P_{c,max}, \\ \max_{a_{m,n} \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}} \left\| \int_{\Omega_m} \int_{B_{a_{m,n}}} \vec{S}_f^{i,j}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\| &\leq P_{o,max}, \\ \max_{a_{k,l}, a_{u,v} \in \mathcal{A}} \left\| \int_{\Omega_i} \int_{B_{a_{k,l}}} \vec{S}_m^{k,l;u,v}(\vec{\kappa}; \omega) d^3 \kappa d\omega \right\| &\leq P_{m,max}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Next, an euclidean metric system in \mathcal{R}^3 can be used to derive a spatial grid to satisfy (7). The distance between the spatial coordinates at \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_2 is

$$d(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2) = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 + (z_1 - z_2)^2} \quad (8)$$

Let \vec{r} denotes the centroid of any surface element. The minimum distances between base stations satisfying the inequalities (7) are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} d_{min,c} &= \min_{\forall \vec{r}_1 \in \mathcal{A}, \vec{r}_2 \in \mathcal{A}'} \{d(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2)\}, \\ d_{min,o} &= \min_{\forall \vec{r}_1 \in \mathcal{A}, \vec{r}_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}} \{d(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2)\}, \\ d_{min,m} &= \min_{\forall \vec{r}_1 \in \mathcal{A}, \vec{r}_2, \vec{r}_3 \in \mathcal{A}_T} \{d(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Notice that for circular antenna foot-prints of identical size, a periodic repetition of the re-use frequency in the spatial grid is expected.

IV Conclusion

A methodology to evaluate the co-channel, the off-channel and the inter-modulation interference of an arbitrary set of transmitter/receiver pairs has been introduced. Since no assumptions are made on the spatial statistics, the presented results are valid for transceivers with uniform as well as non-uniform distribution in space. By using the proposed spectrum assignment, transmitters serving large number of users will receive proportionally more spectral resources. This flexibility is especially important to a global positioning satellite network connecting countries with different telecommunication standards.

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TABLE 1: SPATIAL/TEMPORAL SPECTRUM FOR COMMUNICATION & DETECTION SYSTEMS

(1) Temporal Spectrum (ω)

VHF	UHF	Microwave	Milli-meter Wave	Infrared	Visible	Ultra-Violet
RF, Microwave Radar & Communication				Optical Communication		

(2) Spatial Spectrum (\vec{k})

VLI	LI	HI	VHI	UHI
Low Spatial Intensity (Resolution) Detection & Communication Systems			High Spatial Intensity Detection & Communication Systems	

(3) Simultaneous Space-Time Spectrum Utilization

$\vec{k} \backslash \omega$	Microwave	Milli-meter Wave	Infrared	Optical
VLI	Low Spatial Intensity & Medium Data Rate		Low Spatial Intensity & High Data Rate	
LI				
HI	Medium Data Rate & High Spatial Resolution		High Speed & High Resolution	
VHI				
UHI				

Figure 1: Scenario of Space-Based Communication.